

Siitonen, V., Ritonummi, S., Salo, M., Pirkkalainen, H., Mauno, S. (2024). Coping with Technostress in the Software Industry: Coping Strategies and Factors Underlying their Selection (Online Replication Package) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14180104>

Final sample demographics (n=715)		Number	Percent
Age (in years)	≤ 25	190	26.6%
	26–35	295	41.3%
	36–45	137	19.1%
	≥ 45	73	10.2%
	I prefer not to disclose	20	2.8%
Gender	Male	504	70.5%
	Female	205	28.7%
	Other	4	0.5%
	I prefer not to disclose	2	0.3%
Employment status	Employed full-time (30+ hours a week)	584	81.7%
	Employed part-time (less than 30 hours a week)	64	8.9%
	Entrepreneur	27	5.2%
	Freelancer	37	3.8%
	Unemployed	2	0.3%
	I prefer not to disclose	1	0.1%
Work experience in current role (in years)	Less than a year	103	14.4%
	1-2 years	181	25.3%
	3-5 years	201	28.1%
	6-10 years	116	16.3%
	Over 10 years	113	15.8%
	I prefer not to disclose	1	0.1%
Nationality	British	82	11.5%
	Portuguese	80	11.2%
	South African	68	9.5%
	American	56	7.8%
	Finnish	56	7.8%
	Polish	54	7.6%
	Italian	44	6.2%
	Spanish	23	3.2%
	Mexican	22	3.1%
	Canadian	17	2.4%
	German	15	2.1%
	Greek	12	1.7%
	Dutch	9	1.3%
	French	8	1.1%
	Hungarian	7	1%
	Estonian	6	0.8%
	Irish	5	0.7%
	Other: 30 nationalities with n < 5 (e.g., Australian, Brazilian, Chilean, Chinese, Croatian, Indian, Latvian, Romanian, and Tunisian)	51	7.2%
I prefer not to disclose	100	14%	

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Job title/role	Developer (e.g., software, system, back-end, front-end, and game developer)	321	44.9%
	Managerial positions (e.g., product owner, project manager, CEO, and tech lead)	96	13.4%
	System tester	76	10.6%
	Analyst	46	6.4%
	Software consultant	35	4.9%
	System designer	24	3.4%
	Miscellaneous: 20 job titles/roles with n < 5 (e.g., 3D modeler, coordinator, researcher, and support specialist)	46	6.4%
	I prefer not to disclose	71	9.9%